

DEVELOPMENT OF A MOTORIZED GINGER (*ZINGIBER OFFICINALE*. R) SLICER

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria is the third largest exporter of ginger in the world after China and India. The production is gradually increasing recently in Nigeria in the main producing zones: Kaduna, Nasarawa, Sokoto, Zamfara, Akwa-Ibom, Oyo, Abia and Lagos states with Kaduna as the lead producer. Only about 10% of ginger grown in Nigeria is consumed fresh locally, while the remaining 90% is processed into dried form. About 20% of the dried ginger is consumed locally for various uses, while the remaining 70% is exported. Drying of the fresh product is important for storage during off season and serve as value addition for local or international trade. Slicing enhances this process, as well saves the energy and time required for drying. Some efforts have been made to mechanize the slicing operation in order to aid the drying process in the past. NCAM as a Centre saddled with the responsibility to mechanize Nigerian agriculture has been approached on a number of occasions to come into the mechanization drive of ginger value chain. Hence, the need to start with the development of a slicer with higher performance efficiency and capacity. An efficient motorized ginger slicer was designed, developed and evaluated with an average performance efficiency of 95.54 % and throughput capacity of 76.37 kg/h at a moisture content of 91.45 %.

KEYWORDS: Development, performance efficiency, motorized, slicer

1. INTRODUCTION

Ginger (*Zingiber officinale Roscoe*) is a root crop. The production in Nigeria has gradually increased in recent time. According to FAOSTAT (2018), based on estimated global production shares of 11.5% Nigeria is the third ginger producing countries in the world behind India (35%) and China (18%). It is predominantly grown in the northern and middle belt region in Nigeria. Kaduna state is the largest producer of ginger in Nigeria. Other ginger-producing states include Nasarawa, Niger, Gombe, Bauchi, Plateau and Benue.

The Two major varieties grown in Nigeria are yellow ginger (*Tafin giwa*) and black ginger (*Yatsun Biri*). According to sector experts in Nigeria, yellow ginger is highly preferred by the market and it has an expected higher yield

per hectare (i.e. about 15 tonnes/ha) than black ginger (11 tonnes/ha). It is locally called *Chianti* in Hausa, *Oso-ala* or *Oso-Chikwu* in Igbo and *Ata'le* in Yoruba languages (Aiyeloja and Bello, 2006; Ahmed, 2018).

Ginger productivity in Nigeria is low compared to the area of land under cultivation (Table 1). In 2007, 45.4% of cultivated land for ginger production globally was from Nigeria (FAOSTAT, 2009). The low productivity of ginger in Nigeria is attributed to factors such as poor agronomic practices, unimproved varieties and laborious farming operations due to low mechanization; also wastage due to post-harvest losses reduce the quality and quantity of the crop. (Ayodele and Sambo, 2014).

Table 1. Area, Production and Productivity of Ginger in Nigeria

Year	Area (ha)	Production (MT)	Productivity
1998	166,000	88,100	0.53
1999	153,000	92,000	0.60
2000	158,000	98,000	0.62
2001	160,000	104,000	0.65
2002	162,000	105,000	0.65
2003	167,000	110,000	0.66
2004	170,000	117,000	0.69
2005	181,000	125,000	0.69
2006	191,000	134,000	0.70
2007	195,000	138,000	0.71
Average	170,300	111,110	0.65

Source: FAO Stat, 2009; Ewuziem and Nwauzor, 2011.

Freshly harvested ginger (Figure 1) has a moisture content (wet basis) of 80-85 % and dry basis for storage of 10-12%. It is peppery and has pungent aroma due to the presence of oleoresin and essential oils in its rhizomes (Emehute, 2002). Nigerian ginger is among the best in the world, with its aroma, pungency and high oil and oleoresin content as distinct features (Fresh Plaza, 2020). 10% of ginger is consumed fresh locally, while 90% is processed into dried form. About 20% of the dried ginger is consumed locally for various uses, while the remaining 70% is exported (Juhee *et al.* 2020; Abubakar *et al.* 2019).

Ginger can be consumed fresh or dried; it is widely used for the preparation of soft drinks and beverages like ginger ale, beer, tea, wine, bitters, cordials and liquors; in candies, pickles, sauces, preservatives and bakery products. New products such as vitaminized effervescent ginger powders are now common. It is used as a major ingredient in traditional medicine in India, China and other parts of the world. The oil is used in pharmaceutical preparations of carminative, rubefacient and stimulant for alcoholic gastritis, dyspepsia and flatulent colic (Igbo *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 1. Fresh Ginger Rhizomes

Various activities are involved in the ginger value chain: land preparation, planting, weeding, harvesting, processing and packaging. All these activities can be mechanized for optimum result and economic diversification. Ginger slicing is very important to aid drying of the bulky rhizomes for further handling. Drying of the fresh product is necessary for storage during off season and serve as value addition for local or international trade. Slicing enhances this process, as well saves the energy and time required for drying.

Some efforts have been made to mechanize the ginger slicing operation in order to aid the drying process: Abubakar *et al.*, (2019) developed a portable ginger slicing machine

with two types of slicing compartments, the spring and cushion to accommodate the irregular thickness of ginger rhizomes. The slicing efficiency and Throughput of 63.5 %, 58.32 kg/h, and 50 % and 67.32 kg/h for cushion and spring compartments respectively at 77.44 % moisture content (w.b). The slicing efficiency was low due to the design using two hoppers and slicing compartments (spring and cushion), this caused irregularities in the slicing.

Silva and Jayatissa, (2017) also designed and developed a ginger slicer for small scale spice processors. A rotary slicer was used to achieve it. Average slicing efficiency, material loss and machine capacity were 87.9 %, 2.8 % and 71.4 kg/h, respectively at 400 rpm while the mean thickness of the slices was 9.6 mm. The machine performed better than Abubakar *et al.* (2019) but the average thickness of the sliced rhizome was too high, there is need to have a thinner sliced rhizomes for ease of drying.

Simonyan *et al.* (2014) developed a motorized ginger rhizomes splitting machine using sawing principle with serrated blade. The splitting efficiency (SE), machine capacity (MC), percent dust (PD) and percent injured (PI) were evaluated using two locally grown ginger rhizomes: Umudike ginger I (UG I) and Umudike ginger II (UG II) at moisture content of 73.64% and 77.13% w.b respectively. An average machine capacity of 89.67 kg/h was obtained with UG I while a higher value of 96.33 kg/h was obtained for UG II. The average splitting efficiency for UG I and UG II was 72.97% and 61.62%, respectively. The average percent dust was 2.56% and 4.82%, respectively for UG I and UG II and average percent injured was 5.72% and 7.63% for UG I and UG II, respectively. The difference in the machine performance using the two varieties may be due to UG II being more lignified thereby posing more resistance to cutting. Also the serrated

splitting mechanism missed larger parts of some of the rhizomes due to its principle of operation causing injuries to the rhizomes and affecting the efficiency of the machine.

National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM) in a way to contribute to the mechanization drive of ginger value chain starts with the development of a slicer with higher performance efficiency and capacity. The main objectives of the research study are, to design and fabricate a simple and efficient motorized ginger slicer and evaluate the slicing efficiency.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Description and Operation of the Machine

The main components of the ginger slicing machine are: frame, hopper, slicing unit, and power transmission units (Figure 2). The machine frame is made of 2.5 x 2.5 mm mild steel angle iron for required rigidity. Mounted on the frame are pillow bearings, gear system, shaft, slicing units, hoppers and a prime mover. The hopper is a cylindrical outlet of 60 mm orifice diameter; this is to limit the rhizome gyration during slicing. The chamber is composed of a blade carved on a 5 mm stainless steel plate with a slicing clearance of 2 mm thickness. A V-belt and pulley assembly were used to transmit the power from the prime mover to the slicing chambers. The prime mover is mounted on a frame slit to facilitate adjustment of the belt tension.

The slicing operation is carried out by the shear action of the blade incorporated on a horizontal stainless steel impeller in the slicing chamber. The blade is fixed to a flushing clearance (thickness) of 2 mm and the orifice of the hopper is designed to prevent any escape of the ginger rhizome. Therefore, no unsliced rhizome was recorded.

Figure 2a. Exploded view of the machine

Figure 2b. Isometric view of the machine

2.2 Design Considerations

The following were considered in the design of the motorized ginger slicer:

1. The irregular shape of the rhizomes;
2. Contamination: The slicing chamber and contact surfaces were made of stainless steel which is corrosion resistant and
3. The power requirement

2.3 Material Selection

For the construction of ginger slicing machine the materials will be selected based on the following factors, which includes;

- Availability of materials locally
- Durability
- Strength
- Safety
- Maintenance and operating cost.

2.4 Design Calculations

i. Hopper

The hopper is a 60 mm cylindrical shaped stainless steel.

$$Volume = \pi \times r^2 \times h \quad (1)$$

Where:

r, is the radius, m, and h is the height, m.

ii. Splitting Speed

$$N_1 D_1 = N_2 D_2 \quad (2)$$

Where,

N_1 is prime mover speed, rpm; N_2 is speed of slicing blade shaft, rpm; D_1 is diameter of prime mover pulley, mm and D_2 is diameter of larger pulley connected to slicing blade shaft, mm.

iii. Shaft design

a Shaft Stresses

The largest alternating (σ_a) and mean stresses (σ_m) are at the outside and are determined by:

$$\sigma_a = K_f \frac{M_a C}{I} \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_m = k_{fm} \frac{M_m C}{I} \quad (4)$$

Where k_f and k_{fm} are bending–fatigue and stress–concentration factor for alternating and mean components respectively, C-shaft radius (m) While σ_a and σ_m are alternating stress and mean stress respectively (Norton, 2006).

b. Maximum Shear Load

$$d^3 = \frac{16}{\pi S_s} \sqrt{(K_b M_b)^2 + (K_t M_t)^2} \quad (5)$$

d – diameter Shaft (m), S_s – allowable shear stress (Nm^{-2})

K_b – Combined shock and fatigue factor applied to bending moment

K_t – Combined shocking and fatigue factor applied torsional moment.

M_b – Bending moment (Nm),

M_t – transitional moment (Nm)

(Khurmi and Ghupta, 2005).

c. Shaft Power

$$P = T\omega \quad (6)$$

Where, ω

$$\omega = \frac{2\pi N}{60} \quad (7)$$

Where, P is Power (W), T, torque (Nm), N, motor speed (rpm) and ω , Angular velocity [rad/sec] (Khurmi and Ghupta, 2005).

iv. Determination of Power Required

Total power required is calculated modifying equations as specified by Akintunde *et al.*, (2006)

$$P_T = P_S + P_p \quad (8)$$

Where,

P_T is total power required by the machine (W),

P_S is power required by the shaft (W)

P_p is power required to slice the ginger rhizomes (W).

P_p is negligible since rhizomes are not resident in slicing chamber but flow through it.

2.5 Test and evaluation procedures

2.5.1 Source of test materials

Fresh ginger rhizomes were sourced from Ganmo, market in Ifelodun local government area of Kwara state for the performance evaluation of the machine.

2.6 Materials for Performance Evaluation

The following materials were used for the performance evaluation of the ginger slicer:

- i. OHAUS MB90 moisture analyser
- ii. Camry digital electronic sensitive weighing scale
- iii. Lotron DT- 2236B tachometer
- iv. Travelwey electronic digital stopwatch
- v. Polyethylene nylon bags
- vi. Fresh ginger rhizomes
- vii. Bowls

2.7 Test Procedure

Uniform operational speed of 295 rpm was recorded at the slicing shaft and used throughout the experiment as prescribed by Simonyan *et al.*, (2014). A 400 g sample was fed into the machine in three replicates. The time for complete slicing operation was also recorded for each replicate. After the operations, the sliced samples were taken to the laboratory for size sorting and analysis. The sliced rhizomes that are thicker than the 2 mm slicing clearance of the machine were separated and weighed to evaluate the slicing efficiency of the machine.

2.8 Calculated Parameters

The slicing efficiency and throughput capacity were calculated from the evaluations using the formulae proposed by Simonyan *et al.*, (2014) and Abubakar *et al.*, (2019) respectively:

$$\text{Slicing Efficiency (SE)} = \frac{\text{mass of sliced ginger within desired range (g)}}{\text{mass of sliced ginger out of desired range (g)}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Throughput Capacity (kg h}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{\text{mass of sliced ginger within desired range (g)}}{\text{time of operation (s)}}$$

$$\% \text{ Material Loss (M}_L\text{)} = \frac{W_L}{W} \times 100$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results

The machine performance was evaluated from slicing efficiency and throughput

capacity of the motorized ginger slicer as shown in table 2 and discussed as follow:

Table 2. Results from the performance evaluation of the ginger slicer

ite	Mass of fresh ginger fed into machine (W)/g	Mass of material from machine outlet chute (W _{oc})/g	Mass of material loss to machine (W _L)/g	%Material loss to the machine (%M _L)	Operation Time (s)	Mass of sliced ginger within desired range (W _{WR})/g	Mass of sliced ginger outside desired range (W _{OR})/g	Throughput Capacity (TC)/ g/s	Slicing Efficiency/ %
	400	393.68	6.32	1.58	18.00	379.70	15.98	21.871	94.93
	400	395.32	4.68	1.17	20.00	382.90	12.42	19.766	95.73
	400	396.13	3.87	0.97	18.00	383.80	12.33	22.007	95.95
ge	400	395.04	4.96	1.24	18.67	382.13	13.58	21.215	95.54

3.2 Discussion

- a) Slicing Efficiency (%): an average slicing efficiency of 95.54 % was recorded on the machine. This is much higher than the efficiency of 87.9 % reported by Silva and Jayatissa (2017) using a slicing mechanism of a rotary cutting disc and a semi-automated conveyor feeding system at moisture content of 71.26 % wb. Simonyan *et al.*, (2014) reported an average splitting efficiency of 72.97 % for locally grown ginger rhizomes, Umudike ginger (UG I) and 61.62 % for Umudike ginger II (UG II) at moisture contents of 73.64 % and 77.13 % wb respectively using sawing principle with serrated blades. Also Abubakar *et al.*, (2019) reported an average efficiency of

63.5 % and 50 % for cushion and spring compartments ginger slicer respectively. This shows an improved slicing efficiency compared to some existing machines.

- b) Throughput Capacity (kg/h): an average throughput capacity of 76.37 kg/h was recorded on the machine. This is lower than the average machine capacity of 89.67 kg/h and 96.33 kg/h reported by Simonyan *et al.*, (2014) using two locally grown ginger, Umudike ginger (UG I) and Umudike ginger II (UG II) respectively. It is also lower than 81.05 kg/h reported by Silva and Jayatissa (2017) for their rotary ginger slicer. However, it has a higher capacity than Abubakar *et al.*, (2019) double compartments ginger slicer which reported a machine capacity of 58.32

kg/h and 67.32 kg/h for cushion and spring compartments respectively. This may be as a result of the small hopper capacity which affects the feeding rate of the machine.

4. CONCLUSION

At the end of the research study, an efficient motorized ginger slicer was designed, developed and tested at a moisture content of 91.45%, an average performance slicing efficiency of 95.54% was obtained with no unsliced ginger rhizomes in the machine. Also an average throughput capacity of 76.37 kg/h was recorded on the machine.

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